

Formation and Transformation of Carbon Ring Compounds. Part I. Selenium Dehydrogenation of 1:2:3:4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-spiro-cyclopentane.

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In recent years a large number of naphthalene and phenanthrene derivatives have been synthesised by the cyclisation of γ -phenyl- and γ -naphthylbutyric acids (Kipping and Hill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 144 ; Krollpfeiffer and Schäfer, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 620 ; Schroeter, Müller and Huang, *Ber.*, 1929 62, 645 ; Haworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1125, 2717; Haworth and Bolam, *ibid.*, p. 2248; Haworth, Letsky and Mavin, *ibid.*, p. 1784, 2720). But the effect of various substituents on the ring closure of these γ -phenyl- and γ -naphthylbutyric acids has not as yet been systematically investigated. Thorpe and others (Atwood, Stevenson and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1755 ; Stevenson and Thorpe, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1717; Kon and Stevenson, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 88) have only studied the effect of a negative substituent *e. g.*, a carboxyl group on the ring formation of γ -phenylbutyric acids and they had concluded that for facile ring closure the presence of a substituent in the β -position along with a carboxyl group is essential. While Haworth and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have cyclised the alkyl derivatives of γ -naphthylbutyric acids to the corresponding ketophenanthrene derivatives.

In the present series of investigation the author, while attempting to synthesise some higher coal-tar hydrocarbons and their derivatives, thought it first desirable to make a thorough investigation of the effect of various substituents on the ring closure of γ -phenyl- and γ -naphthylbutyric acids. The influence of *gem*-disubstituents and carbocyclic substituents on the formation of ring compounds from these acids had not been studied previously and first of all specially these types of compounds are being synthesised and their cyclisation studied.

The three well known methods for the ring closure of the γ -substituted butyric acids are as follows:

(i) Cyclisation by the action of anhydrous aluminium chloride on the acid chlorides (Kipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 680; Kipping

and Hill, *loc. cit.*; Kipping and Hunter, *ibid.*, 1901, 79, 602 ; von Braun and Stuckenschmidt, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1724 ; Ruzicka, Ramondt and Wick, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1930, 13, 1117 ; Ruzicka and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1930, 13, 1402 ; 1932, 15, 140 ; 1933, 16, 268, 314).

(ii) With concentrated sulphuric acid, ring closure takes place generally with a poor yield due to the simultaneous sulphonation of the products (Krollpfeiffer and Schäfer, *loc. cit.*; Atwood, Stevenson, Thorpe and Kon, *loc. cit.*; Shröter, *Ber.*, 1921 54, 2243).

(iii) Haworth and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have used 85% sulphuric acid at the temperature of the steam-bath.

In the present investigation 85% sulphuric acid at 100° has been successfully used for the cyclisation of $\beta\beta$ -cyclopentane- γ -phenylbutyric acid (II) to form 1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-spiro-cyclopentane (III), giving 60% of the theoretical yield. In this case we have got a cyclopentane ring in the $\beta\beta$ -position of the γ -phenylbutyric acid and the ring closure proceeds quite satisfactorily. The influence of other carbocyclic groups is also under investigation.

The spiro-hydrocarbon, 1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-spiro-cyclopentane (IV) obtained by the reduction of the above keto compound (III) exhibited most interesting ring transformation on selenium dehydrogenation and furnished phenanthrene and anthracene by a vicinal or angular recombination after the opening up of the cyclopentane ring. The cyclopentane ring was not dehydrogenated till it opened up and was transformed to a six membered ring. Similar observation regarding failure to dehydrogenate a five membered ring had been made by Ruzicka and Thomann (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 11, 224). Clemo and Ormston (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1781) indicate the probability of similar ring transformation of 1-ketocyclohexane-2:2-spiro-cyclopentane (VII) by selenium dehydrogenation to naphthalene, though they had not practically verified it. This observation of the ring transformation of the spiro-hydrocarbon (IV) is of importance considering the present view of the structure of the sterols and bile acids, which are considered as containing a phenanthrene ring in the molecule. This view, however, follows from the fact that the Diels's hydrocarbon (Diels, Gadke and Körding, *Annalen*, 1927, 459, 1), obtained by the selenium dehydrogenation of the sterols and bile acids, had been formulated to be a phenanthrene derivative (Rosenheim and King, *Chem. Ind.*, 1932, 51, 464; Wieland and Dane, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1932, 210, 268). Even if

Diels's hydrocarbon be a phenanthrene derivative (Ruzicka, Ehmann, Goldberg and Hösli, *Helv Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 833; Kon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1081; Cook and Hewett, *ibid.*, 1933, 1098) it cannot be definitely concluded that this phenanthrene ring structure is also pre-existent in the sterols and bile acid molecules. It is not improbable that a naphthalene-*spiro-cyclopentane* ring is present in the molecule which during selenium dehydrogenation forms a phenanthrene derivative.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

For the synthesis of $\beta\beta$ -cyclopentane- γ -phenylbutyric acid, the method for the synthesis of γ -substituted butyric acids by the action

of the anhydrides of substituted succinic acids on aromatic compounds has been utilised (Borsche and Saurenheimer, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 1645; Mayer and Stamm, *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1424; Haworth and co-workers, *loc. cit.*; Oppenheim, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 4228).

The anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid* (Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2599) was condensed with benzene in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, giving *cyclopentane-1-benzoyl-1-acetic acid* (I, R=H). That the reaction does not proceed in the alternative way, giving *cyclopentane-1-acetophenone-1-carboxylic acid* (VI), follows from the synthesis of the keto acid (I) by the following unambiguous method. The acid chloride of the methyl acid ester of *cyclopentane-1-carboxy-1-acetic acid*, having the constitution represented by formula (V) (Bardhan, *loc. cit.*) reacts with benzene in presence of aluminium chloride giving the methyl ester of *cyclopentane-1-benzoyl-1-acetic acid* (I, R=Me), which on hydrolysis gave *cyclopentane-1-benzoyl-1-acetic acid* (I, R=H). This keto acid on reduction by Clemmensen's method (Clemmensen, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 1837) gave *cyclopentane-1-benzyl-1-acetic acid* (II), which on cyclisation with 85% sulphuric acid gave 1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-*spiro-cyclopentane* (III), this on reduction by Clemmensen's method gave 1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-*spiro-cyclopentane* (IV). Selenium dehydrogenation of this *spiro-compound* at 300-50° gave mainly phenanthrene and a little anthracene.

Most interesting results are expected by the selenium dehydrogenation of the corresponding *spiro-cyclohexane* compounds and investigations in that direction are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

cyclopentane-1-benzoyl-1-acetic acid (I, R=H).—(a) Powdered aluminium chloride (27 g.) was slowly added to a mixture of benzene (35 c.c.) and the anhydride of *cyclopentane-1-acetic-1-carboxylic acid* (31 g.) (Bardhan, *loc. cit.*) cooled in ice-water. Hydrogen chloride was evolved at the ordinary temperature. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and the reaction completed by warming the mixture on the water-bath at 60-65° for 3 hours. The viscous brown product was treated with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid and the excess of benzene removed by steam distillation. The white solid was collected, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, extracted with hot sodium carbonate solution and precipitated with

dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid was crystallised from rectified spirit as white plates, m.p. 165-66°, yield 28 g. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 6.8, $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.9 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the methyl alcoholic solution in the usual manner, crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 162° (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.0; H, 6.4. $C_{15}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires C, 62.2; H, 6.6 per cent).

(b) Powdered aluminium chloride (6 g.) was slowly added to a mixture of excess of benzene (20 c.c.) and the acid chloride of the methyl acid ester of *cyclopentane-1-acetic-1-carboxylic acid* (7.3 g.), cooled in ice water. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight and then heated to 60-65° for 3 hours, decomposed with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid and the excess of benzene distilled off in steam. The residual oil was extracted with ether, the ether extract washed with soda solution, dried, ether removed and the keto-ester distilled at 182-83°/5mm. as a thick oil which readily solidified, m.p. 39-40°. (Found: C, 72.9; H, 7.0. $C_{15}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 73.2; H, 7.3 per cent). The ester was hydrolysed with alcoholic potash, the alcohol distilled off, residue dissolved in water and on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid the acid separated out, which was crystallised from spirit, m.p. 165-66°, the mixed m.p. with the keto acid prepared by method (a) was not depressed.

cyclopentane-1-benzyl-1-acetic acid (II).—The previous keto acid (35 g.), amalgamated zinc (175 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (175 c.c.) were allowed to stand at the ordinary temperature for 3 hours and then boiled for 18 hours. After cooling the acid was filtered, dissolved in boiling sodium carbonate solution, acidified with hydrochloric acid and the white precipitated acid crystallised from dilute alcohol as fine long needles, m.p. 99-100°, yield 25 g. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 8.1. $C_{14}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 77.0; H, 8.2 per cent.).

1-Keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-spiro-cyclopentane (III).—The foregoing acid (18 g.) was slowly added to a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (54 c.c.) and water (18 c.c.) and heated on the steam bath for 1½ hours., diluted with ice water and the separated oil extracted with ether, washed with dilute ammonia, dried, ether removed and distilled under reduced pressure. It is a thin colourless oil having a characteristic smell, b.p. 140-41°/4mm., yield 10 g. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 8.0. $C_{14}H_{16}O$ requires C, 84.0; H, 8.0 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 173-74°.

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-spiro-cyclopentane (IV).—The former spiro-keto compound (9 g.), amalgamated zinc (50 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) were boiled for 24 hours, diluted with water, extracted with ether, the ether solution washed, dried, ether removed when the residue distilled at 113-14°/4 mm. as a colourless oil (5 g.) and a little unreduced keto compound (1g.) having a higher b.p. (Found: C, 90·1 ; H, 9·7. $C_{14}H_{18}$ requires C, 90·3 ; H, 9·7 per cent).

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydronaphthalene-3:3-spiro-cyclopentane (3 g.) was heated with selenium (7 g.) in a metal-bath at 300-350° for 40 hours. The product was repeatedly extracted with ether, ether removed, and the residual oil distilled over sodium under reduced pressure ; the first part a liquid distillate (A) contains phenanthrene and some undehydrogenated product and the second fraction (B) which solidifies in the side tube of the distilling flask contains mixture of phenanthrene and anthracene. The fraction (A) was treated with alcohol and picric acid and the separated yellow picrate was recrystallised from alcohol. On decomposing this picrate with dilute ammonia a solid hydrocarbon was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol and identified as phenanthrene, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of phenanthrene was 100°. (Found: C, 94·3 ; H, 5·6. $C_{14}H_{10}$ requires C, 94·4 ; H, 5·6 per cent). The m.p. of the picrate and the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of the picrate of phenanthrene was 145°.

The fraction (B) was dissolved in a little warm benzene and allowed to crystallise, the first crop was collected and recrystallised from benzene ; this was identified as anthracene, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of anthracene was 213°.

The author desires to express his thanks to Dr. P. Neogi and Dr. M. Q. Khuda for the kind facilities they have given for carrying on this work and to Dr. J. C. Bardhan for his kind help and interest in this investigation.